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FACTORS RESPONSIBLE FOR EMPLOYEE EMPOWERMENT IN SELECTED BANKS OF SOUTH GUJARAT

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ABSTRACT

Over the passage of time, all the banks have been adopting employee empowerment with the aim of delivering good services to the valuable customers and ultimately it leads to the customer satisfaction, improving performance, job satisfaction and promoting innovativeness. Many factors have been said to contribute greatly to employee empowerment which has become widely studied in the recent past as one of the ways organizations may use to turn around their performance. This study analyzed mainly five of these factors that influence employee empowerment in an organization. The focus was on the banking sector in selected banks of south Gujarat. The paper also sought to find out the level of employee empowerment exists in different public, private and co-operative banks of south Gujarat. The specific objectives of the study included determining major factors affecting employee empowerment. The Descriptive survey method was being applied to carry out the research. The population comprises selected employees of selected banks of south Gujarat. Data will be analyzed by using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS version 15) after which appropriate interpretation was be done. The study found that main factors affecting employee empowerment in the selected banks of south Gujarat are authority and participation, management supports, control over job, job knowledge and reward& recognition.

Key words: Authority and participation control over job, customer satisfaction, employee empowerment, job knowledge, management supports, service quality and reward& recognition.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Employee empowerment is a key feature of the modern management style. Empowered employees are expected to perform more effectively as compared to those working in traditional or authoritarian organizational cultures.

Service sector plays a significant role in the development of an economy. The front line employees in service organizations, who have direct contact with their customers, serve as the

representatives of the firm's products and services. Employee empowerment improves service quality, which ultimately results in customer satisfaction. In the banking sector, without empowerment, employees lack confidence, creativity and get bounded, which leads to underperformance. Employees will only be successful in dealing with their customers when the management gives authority and necessary support to them, which is termed as "employee empowerment" (peters and mazdarani, 2008). The practices of employee empowerment directly affect the quality of services delivered and customer satisfaction. Hence companies today know that they can compete effectively by making themselves more distinct with respect to service quality and customer satisfaction. Geralis and terziovski (2003) suggest that banks must concentrate on improving their performance because the customer expectations and the competitions among the banking sector increases with the passage of time.

Employees who are empowered in an organization can either portray a positive or negative picture to the customers. Participative management is one of the most popular and most commonly practiced management styles in modern organizations. Empowered employees are more motivated as compared to those who just follow the given lines. Employee empowerment creates sense of belongingness and ownership towards the parent organization. Empowered employee feel more confident and try to give their best to their employers, as a result, service quality improves. Improved product or service quality generally results into higher level of customer satisfaction. Higher level of customer satisfaction results into a bigger sales volume resulting into an improved profitability. Every business aims at earning profits; however profits and customer value go hand in hand. In order to give maximum value to a customer, the service provider is required to develop a sound understanding of the customer expectations. Once customer expectations are known, then some legitimate freedom of action along with the input of employee in the service or product would create a more favourable environment for the success.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Looy et al (2003:143,) "empowerment means providing service employees with enough autonomy to allow them to handle unforeseen problem situations such as complaints". It refers to employees being more proactive and self-sufficient in assisting an organization to achieve its goals, as Herrenkohl et al, (1999:373) explains.

Hailed as the blueprint for employee initiative, empowerment entails "a practice, or set of practices involving the delegation of responsibility down the hierarchy so as to give employees increased decision-making authority in respect to the execution of their primary work tasks" (Leach, Wall, & Jackson 2003, p. 28).

Proponents for empowerment claim that employees who feel empowered at work are more likely to exhibit positive reactions to their job, such as increased identification (Liden et al., 2000; Spreitzer, Kizilos, & Nason, 1997).

Grönroos (2001:349) points out that employees' need to be empowered to perform, but they also need the support of good management, support systems, technology, and information.

The notion of service quality through improved employee productivity has gained momentum among Extension professionals and Extension researchers (Terry & Israel, 2004). While researchers (Seibert et al., 2004) have explored productivity and other work-related outcomes, a deeper understanding of the relationship between empowerment and service quality is needed to build a stronger case for the implementation of an empowered workforce.

Grönroos (2001:346) views employee empowerment as a part of the internal marketing process in an organization which when correctly implemented can have a decisive impact on job satisfaction of employees which may in turn improve the part-time marketing impact of employees in customer -contact.

Satisfied employees tend to be more involved, dedicated, have greater organizational commitment, more loyal and productive towards customer needs, thus enhancing customer satisfaction, which is the ultimate aim of businesses today (Naeem,2010; Yee 2008; Kim, 2004; Lings, 1999; Heskett, 1997). Harter et al. (2002) found that employee satisfaction resulted in higher productivity and reduction in employee turnover.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 The Objectives of the Study was:

- To identify factors responsible for employee empowerment in selected banks of south Gujarat.
- To know the level of employee empowerment in selected banks of south Gujarat.
- To identify the difficulties faced by the employees of the bank in adopting employee empowerment approach.

3.2 Research Design:

A descriptive research design has been used in this study to identify important factors responsible for the employee empowerment in selected banks of south Gujarat.

3.3 Unit of Study:

The target population of this study includes employees of the selected banks of south Gujarat.

3.4 Sample Selection

Non-probability sampling techniques have been used like convenience sampling to collect the Data from the employees of the selected banks with the help of structured questionnaire. Attempt

has been made to collect samples from the 27 branches of selected banks. Sample size was 360 employees of selected banks. Some employees have been interviewed to get the idea about the difficulty faced by them in adopting employee empowerment approach.

3.5 Collection of data

Primary data were collected with the help of structured questionnaire .the secondary information was obtained from the reports of RBI, different branches, websites, journals and magazines. Questionnaire consists of 59 statements. Five options given to the respondent on the bases of 5 point likert scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. With the help of pretested structured questionnaire, researcher tried to know the different aspects of employees regarding their empowerment levels with respective bank.

3.6 ANALYSIS OF DATA

Factor analysis (employee empowerment)

The data was analyzed using SPSS software with the help of factor analysis technique to identify factors important to measure level of employee empowerment in selected banks of south Gujarat. Initially the compatibility of data set is tested, so that it can be determined whether factor analysis can be used for analysis or not. The sample size is 360 employees and variable used is 59, which satisfy the first two conditions that sample size should be more than 100 and ratio between them should be atleast5:1.

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.743
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	7960.904
	Df	1596
	Sig.	.000

Principal component analysis requires that the Kaiser-meyer-olkin measure of sampling adequacy be greater than 0.50 for the set of variables. From the above table we can see that as KMO value is more than 0.5, i.e. 0.743 therefore it is meaningful to run factor analysis. Moreover the significance value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 and therefore we reject HO which shows that interrelated matrix is not identity matrix. It is another indication of the result of factor analysis.

Principal component analysis requires that the probability associated with the Bartietts test of sphericity be less than the level of significance. as shown in the table, this requirement

also gets satisfied. Therefore, the preliminary analysis proves that factor analysis can be satisfactorily used for the present data.

Communalities

Variables	Initial	Extraction
I am free to suggest improvements to boss without fear.	1.000	.577
I have authority to correct problems when they occur.	1.000	.503
I am allowed to do creative when I deal with problems during my job.	1.000	.656
I am allowed to do for doing a high quality job.	1.000	.545
The system of my bank is transparent so as to increase my competencies.	1.000	.341
Bank gives us nonmonetary reward like promotion for the extra achievements.	1.000	.505
I don't need to get managements approval before I handle the problems.	1.000	.791
I have a huge control over how to do my job.	1.000	.498
Bank organizes various functions to recognize and celebrates the success.	1.000	.542
Bank gives us special occasional reward like Diwali bonus etc.	1.000	.615
New ideas are often dismissed.	1.000	.351
I go through a big effort to change the things.	1.000	.486
I Know my work very well.	1.000	.568
Everything is not negotiable here & some matters are rigid.	1.000	.455
I am free to make changes on my job whenever I want.	1.000	.517
I am free to meet the customer's needs and demands under the banks regulations.	1.000	.470
Common rooms are shared.	1.000	.656
I stay back beyond my work time limit.	1.000	.625
I am involved in the organization strategy preparation.	1.000	.595
I can permit visitors, if I feel so, without any ones consent.	1.000	.288
There is restriction for participation in all activities.	1.000	.510
I have huge responsibility in my job.	1.000	.394
Responsibility of each action rests with all.	1.000	.450
I hardly know what my responsibility is.	1.000	.526
I know what my departmental responsibility is.	1.000	.475
I am not free to handle job-related problems by myself.	1.000	.510
Management hardly recognizes hard work.	1.000	.568
You need to follow rules/regulation in the organization.	1.000	.622
Management is open to ideas & more Information sharing.	1.000	.565
I know my next increment date and amount.	1.000	.475
I am encouraged to take independent responsibility.	1.000	.352
I can freely discuss with management regarding customers feedback.	1.000	.578
I am encouraged to develop my way of work.	1.000	.444
Management does not share confidential matters with me.	1.000	.585
I can promise the customers on behalf of the management.	1.000	.635
Bank gives us training about how to solve the customers' problems.	1.000	.687
My bank provides me training when new service is offered to customers.	1.000	.499
I can set my own work standards.	1.000	.545
I know my next promotion period.	1.000	.485

I know my next bonus payment.	1.000	.854
I can meet and interact with customers freely.	1.000	.763
I can attend any meetings in the organization.	1.000	.485
The management provides security of job	1.000	.428
Management does not create fear some times.	1.000	.533
I am allowed to do for doing a high quality job.	1.000	.458
I am allowed to do creative when I deal with problems during my job.	1.000	.544

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Communalities represent the proportion of the variance in the original variables that is accounted for by the factor solution. The factor solution should explain at least half of each original variables variance, so the communality value for variable should be more than 0.50 or higher. We can see that majority of the communality values are more than 0.5 and nearer to 1 so it indicates validation of factor analysis.

Total variance explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	7.459	21.086	21.086	7.459	20.086	20.086	5.997	20.521	20.521
2	3.958	13.089	34.175	3.958	12.943	33.029	3.898	12.838	33.359
3	2.191	9.943	44.118	2.191	8.844	41.913	3.622	8.355	41.714
4	2.119	6.454	50.572	2.119	4.718	50.572	2.106	4.694	50.388
5	1.972	3.459	54.031	1.972	3.459	54.031	2.076	3.643	54.031
6	1.854	3.253	54.304						
7	1.661	2.915	57.219						
8	1.567	2.749	57.968						
9	1.516	2.660	58.628						
10	1.463	2.566	58.694						
11	1.393	2.443	58.737						
12	1.309	2.297	59.134						
13	1.217	2.134	59.268						
14	1.179	2.069	59.337						
15	1.131	1.984	59.420						
16	1.110	1.947	59.568						
17	1.096	1.922	59.990						
18	1.023	1.794	61.784						
19	.991	1.739	63.523						
20	.981	1.721	65.244						
21	.937	1.643	66.888						
22	.930	1.632	68.520						
23	.904	1.586	70.106						
24	.858	1.505	71.611						
25	.843	1.478	73.089						

26	.809	1.419	74.508					
27	.793	1.392	75.900					
28	.777	1.362	77.262					
29	.758	1.330	78.592					
30	.738	1.294	79.886					
31	.704	1.235	81.121					
32	.677	1.188	82.309					
33	.656	1.150	83.459					
34	.633	1.111	84.570					
35	.619	1.085	85.655					
36	.614	1.077	86.732					
37	.601	1.054	87.786					
38	.566	.994	88.780					
39	.537	.942	89.722					
40	.505	.886	90.607					
41	.489	.858	91.465					
42	.454	.797	92.261					
43	.435	.764	93.025					
44	.426	.748	93.773					
45	.408	.716	94.488					
46	.404	.708	95.197					
47	.383	.672	95.869					
48	.374	.657	96.525					
49	.364	.638	97.164					
50	.339	.594	97.758					
51	.297	.521	98.279					
52	.280	.492	98.771					
53	.264	.463	99.234					
54	.237	.415	99.649					
55	.182	.320	99.968					
56	.015	.026	99.994					
57	.003	.006	100.000					

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

From the above table we can see that SPSS output of the total variance explained by the component extracted from the input data. The 5 component explain 54.031 of the total variance in the variables which are included in the component. So it is reasonable enough to go with the analysis.

Rotated component matrix(a)

	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
I am allowed to do for doing a high quality job.	.670				
I am allowed to do creative when I deal with problems during my job.	.669				
I have authority to correct problems when they occur.	.636				
I don't need to get managements approval before I handle the problems.	.631				
I go through a big effort to change the things.	.588				
I am not free to handle job-related problems by myself.	.578				
I am free to suggest improvements to boss without fear.	.568				
I am free to make changes on my job whenever I want.	.529				
I have authority to correct problems when they occur.					
I hardly know what my responsibility is.					
SA42					
I can meet and interact with customers freely.					
Responsibility of each action rests with all.					
I can permit visitors, if I feel so, without any ones consent.					
Bank gives us nonmonetary reward like promotion for the extra achievements.					
I Know my work very well.					
SA44					
There is restriction for participation in all activities.					
I am involved in the organization strategy preparation.					
I know what my departmental responsibility is.					
Management does not share confidential matters with me.		.733			
Management is open to ideas & more Information sharing.		.709			
The management provides security of job		.614			
Management does not create fear some times.		.593			
I stay back beyond my work time limit.					
I know my next bonus payment.					
I am allowed to do creative when I deal with problems during my job.					
You need to follow rules/regulation in the organization.			.597		
I am free to meet the customer's needs and demands under the banks regulations.			.557		
I have a huge control over how to do my job.			.554		
I have huge responsibility in my job.			.544		
Management hardly recognizes hard work.					
Bank organizes various functions to recognize and celebrates the success.					
I am encouraged to take independent responsibility.					
The system of my bank is transparent so as to increase my competencies.					
I am encouraged to develop my way of work.				.626	

My bank provides me training when new service is offered to customers.				.582	
Bank gives us training about how to solve the customers' problems.				.501	
I can freely discuss with management regarding customers feedback.					
Bank gives us special occasional reward like Diwali bonus etc.					
Common rooms are shared.					
New ideas are often dismissed.					
I can promise the customers on behalf of the management.					
I know my next increment date and amount.					.572
I know my next promotion period.					.566
Everything is not negotiable here & some matters are rigid.					
I can set my own work standards.					
I can attend any meetings in the organization.					

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a Rotation converged in 16 iterations.

We can use above table to extract the relevant variables to be loaded on each factor. We attribute variables which have loading more than 0.500 to a particular factor. From the above table we can see that total 21 variables are divided between 5 factors. Below table shows that factor 1 includes 8 variables. Factor 2 includes 4 variables. Factor 3 includes 4 variables. Factor 4 includes 3 variables. Factor 5 includes 2 variables.

Factors extracted

	Factors				
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
Communalities					
Factor 1 authority & participation					
Authority for doing high quality job	0.670				0.545
Authority to do creative things	0.669				0.656
Authority to correct problems	0.636				0.503
Don't need approval for problem solving	0.631				0.791
Go through big efforts to change things	0.588				0.577

Not free to handle job related problems	0.578	0.510
Free to suggest improvement to boss	0.568	0.577
Free to make changes	0.529	0.517
Factor 2 management support		
Sharing confidential information's with me	0.733	0.585
Open to receive ideas and information's	0.709	0.565
Provide security of job	0.614	0.528
Does not create fear	0.593	0.533
Factor 3 control over job		
Need to follow rules	0.597	0.622
Free to meet customers need	0.557	0.570
Huge control over job	0.554	0.498
Huge responsibility over job	0.544	0.594
Factor 4 job knowledge		
Encouragement to develop my way of work	0.626	0.444
Training for new product	0.582	0.499
Training for solving customers problem	0.501	0.687
Factor 5 reward and recognition		
Awareness about next increment	0.572	0.485
Awareness about next promotion	0.566	0.854

4. CONCLUSIONS

The present study aimed at identifying factors related to employee empowerment from the point of view of the employees of selected banks of south Gujarat. In order to identify major factors, principal component analysis or factor analysis is used as statistical tools. The data is collected through the survey of employees of the selected banks of south Gujarat through well structured questionnaire.

The factor analysis results showed that there are 5 important factors related to employee empowerment. The study proves significant for selected banks who have interest to adopt employee empowerment in their system and who are planning to achieve high level of employee empowerment. There are lots of opportunities for banks to get competitive advantage with the

use of employee empowerment approach in a better way. However, since the 5 factors account for only 54 % of the variance and the survey has been conducted only for the surat city.

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